

WOMEN'S PARTICIPATION IN SOCIAL PROCESSES

N.Ismoilova¹

¹Master's student of Psychology, Urganch State University

I.Rajapova²

²Master's student of Psychology, Urganch State University

M.Raxmonova³

³Psychologist of general secondary school No. 12 of Khiva district

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7519188>

Abstract: The article highlights the importance of women's participation in the social processes of society. Due to the fact that there have been various influences on their professional activities over the centuries, obstacles to women's participation in social spheres and self-expression have been psychologically analyzed.

Keywords: Talent, professional growth, self-awareness, performance, sustainability, strategy, career, career.

It is known from the history of mankind that there is a great demand for creative and talented people. In order for the society to be stable, to develop, and for the people to live a prosperous life, talented people are needed in every aspect. Talent does not choose age, nationality, gender or place. Women are also making great strides in talent and creativity.

Today we can meet women in almost all areas of our society. In recent years, the attitude towards women has changed radically. It should be noted that at the 63rd session of the UN Commission on the Status of Women held on March 11-17, 2019, in which the delegation of our country participated, UN Secretary General Antonio Guterres said, "Where women are active in political and social life the economy is growing, stability is being strengthened and the well-being of citizens is increasing in that place," he said. [1]

Professional activity is one of the spheres of self-awareness of a person, his personalization. In professional activity, a person has the opportunity to reveal and show his abilities, personal and professional qualities. This activity allows a person to recognize his uniqueness and importance for other people. It helps to confirm some form of compensation for society as a whole. [2]

According to an empirical study conducted by Marina Malysheva in the mid-1990s, family-oriented women perceive discrimination in the labor market as something natural. The dominance of men, the priority position in enterprises is a constant reality for them, they follow it throughout their conscious life and consider it the most rational model of society. Not only housewives, but also highly educated young women with high social aspiration and professional ambitions prefer to have a partner who earns more than themselves. On the other hand, men treat women's income as a secondary and optional type of family income, not an equal contribution to the family budget, but a "help". In Uzbekistan, men are the main breadwinners of the family. [2]

The analysis of women's professional activity in the current period shows that the problem of employment in modern Russia, especially the problem of providing women with qualified professional work, is extremely acute. They are deprived of the opportunity to show their abilities, to realize their professional knowledge, experience and skills. This is due to the conservatism of views on the distribution of family roles, blind adherence to patriarchal

traditions. This situation, without a doubt, hinders the progressive social development of the state.[5]

In many countries of the world, the social status of women is not high. This means that a woman is not a full-fledged member of society. Often, women do not choose professional growth as their main life strategy. [3]

According to I.F. Rekovskaya, every second man with higher or secondary specialized education is a leader. Only 7% of graduates are female managers. Even in schools with a preponderance of female teachers, only 39% of female principals are female. [7]

W. O'Leary explored the relationship between gender stereotypes and the reasons why women are delayed in moving up the corporate ladder in industry. In his opinion, without any objective grounds, the following attitudes towards work belong to women: they work only for "pin" money (that is, a small salary); in their work they are more interested in purely communicative and emotional moments; women prefer work that does not require intellectual strength; they value self-expression and promotion less than men. These are false ideas about women's lack of competence, independence, competitiveness, logic, assertiveness, etc.[2]

Despite a higher level of education, women have a stronger self-assessment of their work opportunities and lack confidence in their value and competitiveness in the labor market. In addition, women take on the entire burden of housework (nowadays 80% of all housework is done by women), which significantly reduces their activity outside the home. The main reason for the low competitiveness of women in the labor market is usually domestic factors. Domestic work is generally unpaid and not considered "real work" [8]

In modern society, a woman really faces a choice: family or work. The superiority of one or another life (career or family) is not always the result of conscious preference. In most cases, this is mandatory and causes psychological discomfort. Immersion in a "career" leads to feelings of loneliness, lack of prospects in personal life and public disapproval. Women who are only busy with the family are not always happy: they lack diversity in communication, complete social self-awareness, underestimation of their personality by other family members, complete material suffer from addiction. However, it is very difficult to combine the roles of a housewife and a good income earner for the family. Thus, a woman who wants to express her abilities and realize her potential often finds herself in conflict with the traditional views of others about the role of women in society. Some women experience stress or role conflict trying to be a good mother, a good housewife, and a good worker at the same time. As a result, they think that they are overloaded at work and at home. This is called "satiation syndrome". [2]

According to M. V. Safonova, the personal qualities of successful women are openness, social courage and activity, prudence, emotional restraint, high level of intelligence, self-control. According to most indicators, this group of women approaches the average values of the male sample, which indicates that they are as strong as men. In addition, the majority of women who are successful in their work have a higher education, and a third of them have a scientific degree. [9]

E. Rannik found that women are more interested in improving sanitary and hygienic working conditions and work organization than men. As N. N. Obozov pointed out, they pay more attention to the evaluation of their work by other participants of joint activities, therefore praise or negative evaluation is the main regulator of their work activity. Women

are very sensitive to relationships at work, so they prefer jobs with good relationships, even at the expense of salary. Orientation to personal, comfortable relationships can compensate for their dissatisfaction in family and marital relationships. [10]

Increasing the role and status of women in socio-political and socio-economic life is a very important priority task at the level of state policy in our country. Effective measures are being taken to strengthen the social activity of women, ensure their employment, strengthen the institution of the family, motherhood and childhood protection. As a result, in March, April, May 2022, the President and the Cabinet of Ministers signed 12 decisions and decrees on women.

Therefore, in order to increase the importance of women's participation in society, it is necessary to change the wrong stereotypes about them. It is necessary to help women to reveal their abilities and talents, to support them in every way.

References:

1. Sh. Mirziyoyev "The work of a people with a great intention will be great, their life will be bright and their future will be prosperous." Tosh "Uzbekistan"-2019 160,161 pages
2. Stepanova L.G. Professional segregation of modern women as a factor based on stereotypical perception of gender roles // Psychology of maturity and aging. - 2006. - No. 4
3. Aleshina Yu.E., Lektorskaya E.V. Role conflicts of the working woman. // Issues of psychology. 1989. - No. 6. - Pages 23-28.
4. Arsanukaeva M.S. To the problem of rational use of women's labor. // Social problems of interdependence of professional and family functions of a woman. M., - ISAI, 1980. - p.27-34.
5. Babaeva L.V. Russian women in the context of social changes: work, politics, everyday life. Public Scientific Foundation of Russia. Scientific reports. Edition. 34. M., - 1996. - 204b.
6. Baskakova M.E. Married woman: family or work? // Family in Russia. -1995 year. -#3-4.
7. Rakovskaya O.A. Peculiarities of women's professional career formation// Gender aspects of social changes. M., 1996. B.58.
8. Ilyin E.P. Differential psychophysiology of men and women. - St. Petersburg: Peter, 2007. - S.399.
9. Safonova, M.V. Socio-psychological characteristics of successful women: diss. ... sincere. a psychologist. Sciences: 19.00.05. - St. Petersburg, 1999. - P. 133.
10. Obozov N.N. Woman + man =?! / N. N. Obozov; Academy of Psychology, Entrepreneurship and Management. - St. Petersburg. : LNPP "Oblik", 2007. - P.74.
11. Gvozdeva E., Gerchikov V. Women's management in Russian business. // ECO: Organization of economy and production. 1997. - No. 11 (287). -Pages 163-177.
12. Civil service: Career and professional growth. Foreign experience. Edition. 14. M.: Academy of the Russian Civil Service under the President of the Russian Federation. - 1997. - 117b.
13. Granovskaya PM, Nikolskaya IM. Personal protection. St. Petersburg: "Knowledge" publishing house, 1999.-347p.
14. Grebenyuk G.A., Samsonova E.Yu. Leadership personality and leadership styles. // Psychological analysis. 1995 - Issue 1. - Pages 14-20.
15. Dalbum-Hall B. Women and Leadership. Per. from English. - St. Petersburg: "Owl" publishing house, 1996. - 132p.

16.

Druzhinin V.N. Experimental psychology. M.: INFRA-M, 1997. -255p.

17. Women's problem: views and approaches to new understanding: Collection of articles. Moscow: Academy of Social Sciences, 1990. - 185p.

18. Women in society: facts, problems, forecasts. M.: Nauka, 1991. -127p.

19. Women and men in the way of sustainable development (gender approach experience). A collection of articles. M.: REFIA, 1997. - 95s.

20. A woman at work. Rostov-on-Don: "Fenix" publishing house, 1996. - 480s.

21. Women and democratization: women's public opinion on current social and political problems. (Results of sociological research). Rep. edited by G. G. Sillaste. - M., 1991. - 106p.

22. Women and social policy. (Tender Aspect): Collection of articles. / Wah. ed. Z.A. Khotkina. M., 1992. - 204b.

